

EXPLORERS

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The Providence Group

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The Providence Group helps organizations navigate the complexity of cybersecurity and privacy risk in order to thrive in today's uncertain environment.

Our approach to risk management empowers executives and builds value through deep organizational insights, foresight of unanticipated risks, and organizational capacity building.

Our cybersecurity and privacy experience is in Congress, the executive branch, regulatory agencies, the intelligence community, and in law firms, management consulting and public relations. We have deep international cybersecurity and privacy relationships in government, trade associations, law firms, cybersecurity software developers, communications and industries across business sectors. We participate in government and private sector cybersecurity and privacy workshops, leading international conferences, and publish frequently on pressing cybersecurity and privacy issues.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGE

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Health

CHALLENGE #11 - TPG-POL-01

→ Connecting Transatlantic policy makers to promote understanding

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Continue connecting senior EU and US policy makers as we have done in previous Horizon 2020 projects

OBJECTIVES

Be pro-active and frame forward looking opportunities and challenges like next generation internet to enhance transatlantic cooperation to promote economic growth

SKILLS REQUIRED

We bring 20+ years of technology policy experience in the US Intel Community, US Department of Commerce, US Federal Trade Commission, US House and Senate, and US industry , European Commissions and European Parliament to connect senior policy makers

